

Impact of Leadership Skill Approach on School Effectiveness at Secondary Level

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Abstract

The current study aimed to examine the impact of the leadership skill approach on the school's effectiveness at the secondary level. Positivism philosophy was used. A sample of 300 SSTs was selected out of 1230 teachers in district DG Khan through a stratified sampling method. A self-developed questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was based on 55 items including three skills of leaders (24 items) and school effectiveness (31 items). The questionnaire was validated by using the Index of Item objective-congruence (IOC) whereas Cronbach's Alpha was used to estimate the reliability of the questionnaire. Linear regression and independent sample t-tests were used as inferential statistics. The study concluded that all three leadership skills (human, technical, and conceptual) have a significant impact on the school's effectiveness. The study recommended that training may be provided to school heads to enhance their technical, human, and conceptual skills.

Keywords: Human Skills, Technical Skills, Conceptual Skills, School Effectiveness

1. Introduction

The leadership of the school is crucial to the entire teaching and learning process. Leadership decisions made by schools have an effect on their capacity and can either improve or worsen student accomplishment. A school's capacity is its staff's overall ability to improve student progress. An effective school leader is one who can grow the capacity of a school to improve student learning through inspiring teachers, staff, and students. The followers, not the leaders, decide what constitutes such leadership (Heikka et al., 2021). Many times, rather than being viewed as an instructional leader, a school administrator is thought of as someone who administers a school. The everyday decisions and activities of the leader show the leadership of the school's overarching focus and manner (Bush & Glover, 2014). According to Tatlah and Iqbal (2012), a leader who is teacher-focused works to improve school performance by developing school capacity that builds on strong teacher capability.

Leadership, in the opinion of Cerit and Yildirim (2017), is both a process and an activity. It is the process of inspiring and directing people to work together for a common purpose under the inspiration and guidance of a leader who is dedicated to achieving this objective. To lead successfully, one requires both talent and abilities. To succeed, one can successfully project a sincere image of a great leader. The Great Man theory has been around since 1840. Following the Great Man idea, a number of additional theories, including the Katz theory, trait theory, behavioral leadership theories, and theories of contingent leadership, were developed. Katz's theory of leadership qualities was applied by the researcher in the current study. Alternatively, it is referred to as Katz's Three-Skill Approach. It is a theory that organizes and describes the managerial abilities needed by skill level and hierarchy (Rasaki & Abioye, 2018). A competent manager possesses the conceptual, human, and technological triplets of managerial abilities, in accordance with Katz's skill theory. The skill idea contends that effective leadership requires a combination of knowledge, abilities, and talents. Gained abilities and knowledge are necessary for effective leadership. It emphasizes the aptitudes and skills that individuals possess and can acquire. Katz (2009), who promoted the idea that effective leadership requires the acquisition and use of three skills i.e., technical, conceptual, and human skills produced the most significant work on the skill method. The three-skills approach of leadership is ignored by the researchers at secondary school level in Pakistan. The current paper aimed to investigate the impact of the leadership skill approach on the school effectiveness. The key objectives of the study were:

- i. To examine the impact of three approaches of leadership (human, conceptual, and technical) on the school's effectiveness
- ii. To compare the three leadership approaches of school principals from the perspective of gender.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Leadership

The concept of leadership encompassed elements such as inspiration, persuasion, influence, and transformation. According to the study, leadership is "the process of developing a vision, communicating change that reflects shared ambitions, and influencing group members to achieve shared objectives. The act of inspiring or motivating others to achieve an organization's objectives is known as leadership. Raising employee motivation and self-worth is the process of enabling them to carry out the tasks and objectives of the firm. The leadership style and competencies of

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a leader have a significant impact on employee motivation. Leadership can be defined as a process whereby one individual motivates others to accomplish group or organizational goals (Fiaz et al., 2017). Noor et al. (2019) claim that leadership is a process that can be observed, comprehended, and that has an impact on individuals, groups, and society. A person who is influence on people and motivate them towards the accomplishment of organizational goals. Every definition, motivation, influence, encouragement are the key terms in the leadership. Thus, an effective leadership has all these characteristics to influence and make bond with people to achievement of the organizational objectives. This suggests that effective leadership entails forging a personal bond with those it is tasked with leading, enabling them to be inspired rather than compelled into accomplishing goals.

2.2. Three Skill Approach of Leadership

Successful leadership necessitates learned skills and knowledge, claims the skill hypothesis (Katz, 2009). Effective leadership requires the knowledge, abilities, and skills of the leader. It strongly emphasizes the learnable and expandable abilities and capacities of individuals (Seyedineja et al., 2014). The most significant work on the skill method was produced by Katz (2009), who argued that successful leadership (administration) is based on three skills: technical, human, and conceptual competencies (Katz's Three Skills theory). The skill idea holds that effective leadership requires a combination of knowledge, abilities, and skills. Gained knowledge and learned abilities are necessary for effective leadership. It emphasizes the aptitudes and skills that people possess and can learn. The most prominent work on the skill method was written by Katz in 1955, who stated that three skills—technical, conceptual, and human skills—must be developed and used for effective leadership (Katz, 2009).

Technical skill is information that is clearly based on expertise in a particular industry. The acts specific to a corporation, such as its rules, policies, goods, and services, require leaders to have knowledge of and expertise in these areas (Katz, 2009). Human skills are interpersonal communication abilities that are founded on an understanding of an individual's knowledge of an individual's motivations, attitudes, and feelings. A leader can influence the group to cooperate towards common objectives by demonstrating their interpersonal skills. Conceptual-skilled leaders can work with and through concepts. School heads with conceptual skills plan for future, making team building and develop vision and mission which support school success. School leader effectively influence by his leadership skill approach, his competency level and vast knowledge about human behavior. No longer is leadership depending upon now individual traits. Thus, now leadership approach requires for school success. Therefore, three leadership skill approach of Katz is essential for principals to run their school successfully (Nwogu & Ebinu, 2019).

2.3. School Effectiveness

School effectiveness cannot be measured only through students' achievement. There are many other factors that influence the overall school effectiveness such as school infrastructure, school environment, competency level of teachers, and school head. If the classrooms are overcrowded, the teachers have low qualifications, and the curriculum changes suddenly then it affects the overall quality of education and can lead to school ineffectiveness (Naz et al., 2021). Moreover, the relationship school and the community is another important factor that influences the school's effectiveness. school effectiveness can be defined as the achievement of pre-established school goals within a stipulated time period (Raynolds, 2010). So, the achievement of pre-established goals and school effectiveness are interconnected. There are different views regarding the school's effectiveness. Some believe that school effectiveness is linked with students' achievement whereas some believe that school effectiveness links the relationship with community and school environment (Mulyani et al., 2020). All factors mentioned above are key components of school effectiveness.

3. Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Conceptual model (Impact of leadership skills approach on school effectiveness)

4. Research Methodology

While conducting this research, the positivist research philosophy was applied. A positivist research philosophy was employed while conducting this study. The research philosophy of positivism values facts and information that could be measured. Consequently, the researcher employed a quantitative research approach. The current research aimed to examine the impact of a leadership skill approach on a school's effectiveness. Thus, the survey research design was used. All secondary school Teachers (SSTs) of District DG Khan were taken as the population of the study. There are 1230 SSTs working in the district DG Khan (School Information System [SIS], Punjab). As per the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size table, a sample of 300 SSTs was selected through a stratified sampling method. A self-developed questionnaire was used including demographic attributes of teachers like gender. Twenty-four (24) items related to three skills approach of leadership and 31 items related to school effectiveness. Questionnaire was validated by using Index of Item objective-congruence (IOC) whereas Cronbach's Alpha was used to estimate the reliability of the questionnaire. Linear regression and independent sample t-test were used as inferential statistics. Table 1 shows the score of IOC and Cronbach's Alpha.

Table 1: IOC and Cronbach's Alpha score

Research variables	No. of Items	IOC	Cronbach's Alpha
Three Skill	5	.60-1.0	.783
Approach	13	.70-1.0	.812
	8	.60-.90	.796
School Effectiveness	31	.50-1.0	.832

Note: .50 is the minimum criteria for valid item (Turner& Carlson, 2003)

5. Result and Discussion

Table 2: Regression output summary regarding the impact of human skill on school effectiveness

IV	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj. R</i> ²	<i>B</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>D-W</i>
Human Skill	.759 ^a	.721	.720	.716	142.33	.000	2.70

Dependent variable: School Effectiveness

Table 2 indicates a regression output summary about the impact of human skills on the school's effectiveness. The table depicts that $R=.759$ which shows a positive association between human skill and school effectiveness. The value of $R^2=.721$ which infers that 72.1% variation occurred in school effectiveness due to the human skill approach of the school head. The value of beta indicates if a single unit increase in human skill occurs then a .716 unit increase in school effectiveness will be occurred. The value of $p < .05$ reveals that human skill has a significant impact on a school's effectiveness. The value of the Durban Watson test (2.70) shows no autocorrelation between the two variables.

Table 3: Regression output summary regarding the impact of technical skill on the school effectiveness

IV	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj. R</i> ²	<i>B</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>D-W</i>
Technical Skill	.658 ^a	.617	.617	.556	78.33	.000	2.31

Dependent variable: School Effectiveness

Table 3 indicates a regression output summary about the impact of technical skills on the school's effectiveness. The table depicts that $R=.658$ which shows a positive association between technical skill and school effectiveness. The value of $R^2=.617$ infer that 61.7% variation occurred in school effectiveness due to the technical skill approach of the school head. The value of beta indicates if a single unit increase in technical skill occurred then a .556 unit increase in school effectiveness will be occurred. The value of $p < .05$ reveals that technical skill has a significant impact on the school's effectiveness. The value of the Durban Watson test (2.31) shows no autocorrelation between the two variables.

Table 4 indicates a regression output summary about the impact of conceptual skills on the school's effectiveness. The table depicts that $R=.795$ which shows a positive association between conceptual skill and school effectiveness. The value of $R^2=.702$ which infers that 70.2% variation occurred in school effectiveness due to the conceptual approach of the school head. The value of beta indicates if a single unit increase in conceptual skill occurred then a

.761 unit increase will be occurred in school effectiveness. The value of $p < .05$ reveals that conceptual skill has a significant impact on the school effectiveness. The value of the Durban Watson test (2.29) shows no autocorrelation between the two variables.

Table 4: Regression output summary regarding the impact of conceptual on the school effectiveness

IV	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj. R</i> ²	<i>B</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>D-W</i>
Conceptual Skill	.795 ^a	.702	.701	.761	93.33	.000	2.29

Dependent variable: School Effectiveness

Table 5: The mean difference in the three-skill approach (human, technical, and conceptual) of the leadership of school principals across gender

Skill approach	Gender	Mean	S.D	<i>t</i> _{cal}	<i>Sig.</i>
Human skill	Male	3.71	1.11	-2.76	.000
	Female	3.21	1.21		
Technical skill	Male	3.88	1.19	1.87	.000
	Female	3.51	1.82		
Conceptual skill	Male	3.66	1.34	1.66	.001
	Female	3.52	1.49		

$p < .05$

Table 5 shows the mean difference in three skill approaches (human, technical, and conceptual) of leadership of school principals across genders. The table reveals that a significant difference was found in the male and female principals regarding human skills ($p < .05$). In addition, the table infers that a significant difference was found in the male and female principals regarding technical skills ($p < .05$) and that significant difference was found in the male and female principals regarding conceptual skills ($p < .05$).

6. Discussion

The study aimed to investigate the impact of the skill approach of leadership (human, technical, and conceptual) on the school effectiveness. The result of the study depicts that human skill has a significant impact on a school effectiveness. The same result was mentioned by Justice (2018) who found that the environment of interpersonal relationships between principals and teachers has a positive impact on the school success. A behavior principal positively influences the teacher's performance which ultimately leads towards school effectiveness. The result of the study depicts that the technical skills of school heads have a positive impact on school effectiveness. A similar result was given by Nwogu and Ebonu (2019). They found that principals with sound technical skills such as dealing with conflicts and utilizing school funds and budgets play a significant role in the school's effectiveness. In contrast, the principal who are unfamiliar with technical skills damages the school's success. the result of the study shows that the conceptual skills of school heads have a significant impact on the school's effectiveness. The same result was found by Ayalew et al. (2014) and Nwogu and Ebonu (2019). They explored that a principal with conceptual skills has a positive impact on the school's effectiveness.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

The study concluded that schools are more effective when their leaders have greater levels of human competence. In other words, a school leader's interpersonal abilities improve academic achievement. According to this study, a school's progress can be increased by fostering a positive work atmosphere and building strong bonds with its stakeholders.

The effectiveness of the school was significantly impacted by conceptual capabilities in addition to two other skill sets (human and technological). According to the study's findings, school leaders who possess analytical abilities, logical thinking, innovative creativity, the ability to handle challenging relationships, problem-solving abilities, the ability to analyze activities, feel trends and anticipate altering accordingly, and the ability to seize chances, are more effective. A school head's conceptual abilities are shaped by those many kinds of capabilities. The study recommended that training may be provided to school heads to enhance their technical, human, and conceptual skills. For this purpose, the government may arrange training and workshops for school principals regarding the improvement of technical and conceptual skills.

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